

Resilience and Coping Strategies of Primary Caregivers of Children with Special Needs

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Abstract

Primary caregivers of children with special needs (CSN) encounter unique challenges that need to be addressed through a social work lens. This study then aimed to uncover these by studying their resilience and coping strategies while taking care of CSN enrolled in special education centers for school year 2024-2025 and propose a program for these primary caregivers. It employed a quantitative approach to address the research problems using the data gathered from parents, guardians, grandparents, other close family members and hired caregivers of CSN. It used a survey questionnaire that included the Parenting Resilience Elements Questionnaire (PREQ) developed by Suzuki et al. (2015) and the Carver Brief COPE Inventory. Results showed that these caregivers are diverse and take care of CSN with varying conditions, mostly having developmental disabilities. They are resilient through knowing their child's characteristics and the social support they receive, and very resilient by having a positive perception of their parenting responsibilities. Further, they lean towards using problem-focused coping strategies, describing them as moderately coping, and only slightly coping using emotion-focused and avoidant coping strategies. In addition, their profile characteristics do not describe their level of parental resilience, and their use of avoidant coping strategies showed significant differences in terms of age, educational attainment, and whether their child has autism or not. Lastly, a comprehensive parenting education program was proposed centered on taking care of the primary caregivers and the CSN.

Keywords: learners with disabilities, parental knowledge, perception, problem-focused coping

Introduction

Parents, both biological and non-biological, nurture a child's physical, emotional, and cognitive growth into adulthood (Merriam-Webster). Children, especially those with special needs, require adult guidance to develop societal responsibilities. Special needs, as defined by UNICEF, involve long-term impairments limiting societal participation, which possess challenges for caregivers (Walker et al.). For caregivers, it involves offering quality parenting despite hardships (Gavidia-Payne et al.). Factors influencing resilience include understanding the child's traits, social support, and positive parenting views (Suzuki et al.). Southeast Asian parents of autistic children face challenges in social support, finances, and future concerns (Ilias et al.). Filipino caregivers draw resilience from family, religion, and community (Nicomedes et al.), but caregiving stress impacts their resilience (Gabriel & Sison). Considering that raising children with special needs often results in stress, financial strain, and stigma (Falk et al.; Goudie et al.). Caregivers face increased mental health risks, worsened during the COVID-19 pandemic (Marquis et al.). Effective support systems are crucial for alleviating stress and improving resilience (Alhuzimi; Borro & Ceballo).

Support networks provide effective ways to manage stress and promote positive caregiving outcomes. Non-judgmental discussions, empathy, venting emotions, and seeking counsel are beneficial (Peer & Hillman, 2014). Sharing problems strengthens relationships and encourages participation in support groups to address challenges like disability-related stress (Billote, 2018). While caregiving has its struggles, it also fosters personal growth, confidence, faith, and meaningful relationships (Beighton & Wills, 2017). Adapting to adversity positively influences the child's quality of life (Cappe et al., 2011; Migerode et al., 2012; Suzuki et al., 2013). Caregivers utilize various strategies to handle stress, including seeking support, altering beliefs, religious practices, or positive reinterpretation of situations (Kamaruddin & Mamat, 2015; Picci et al., 2015). Religious and social

support systems play significant roles in coping (Lasco et al., 2022). Financial, medical, social, and educational challenges are inherent to living with a child's disability, requiring a lengthy adjustment period.

Exploring resilience among Filipino caregivers reveals their reliance on family, faith, and community during adversity. Post-pandemic research is limited, but resilience studies can guide social work in creating effective programs to address gaps in caregiver-specific services. Current social welfare efforts focus largely on financial assistance, highlighting the need for tailored initiatives to support caregivers. Recommendations include developing programs to ease caregivers' burdens, which could be proposed to municipal social welfare offices for action.

The research seeks to assess resilience and coping strategies among primary caregivers of children with special needs (CSNs) enrolled in SPED centers in Bayombong and Solano. Conducted during the 2024 school year, from August to October, the study focuses on understanding caregivers' experiences and proposing community programs to support them through Demographic Profile, assessing parental resilience in terms of knowledge of the child's characteristics, perceived social support and positive perception of parenting.

Methodology

The study employed a quantitative, descriptive-comparative research design to examine the resilience and coping strategies of primary caregivers of children with special needs (CSNs). Conducted in Bayombong and Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, it focused on caregivers of children enrolled in SPED centers such as Bayombong Central School which caters 87 children with sensory impairments and Solano East Central School serving 56 children with developmental disorders (e.g., autism, Down syndrome, ADHD). Involving 143 caregivers, including parents, grandparents, other family members, and hired caregivers of children officially diagnosed and enrolled in SPED centers. Using Raosoft.com, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, a sample size of 105 was determined wherein at least 63 participants from Bayombong SPED Center and 42 participants from Solano SPED Center.

Participants were aged 18 years and above, of varying marital statuses, selected based on willingness to share experiences. Purposive sampling was applied, and informed consent was secured. The data collections tools include the Profile Questionnaire for the demographic and basic information of participants, Parenting Resilience Elements Questionnaire (PREQ) by Suzuki et al. (2015), a 16-item Likert scale assessing resilience factors like adaptation to challenges and Carver Brief COPE Inventory, a 28-item scale evaluating coping strategies, such as problem-focused and emotion-focused responses.

Before gathering data, the researchers obtained approval from the Department of Education (SDO) and school principals. Orientation sessions on the study's purpose were conducted with participants, who provided informed consent. Caregivers then completed survey questionnaires, which were collected, securely stored, and prepared for analysis.

To examine the data gathered, descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the profile of the primary caregivers, frequency counts and percentages and for the level of parental resilience and level of coping strategies, means and standard deviations were used. Means is interpreted as found in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. For the tests of significant differences, since the respondents are purposely selected, non-parametric tests were used. These are Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis H Test.

Table 1*Mean Ranges and Qualitative Descriptions for Level of Parental Resilience*

Mean Ranges	Qualitative Description
1.00-1.49	Extremely Not Resilient – Highly not Resilient
1.50-2.49	Not resilient - Resilient
2.50-3.49	Slightly Resilient
3.50-4.49	Neutral/Moderately Resilient
4.50-5.49	Resilient
5.50-6.49	Very Resilient
6.50-7.00	Extremely Resilient – Highly Resilient

*Source: Azlizam et al. (2018) for a 7-point Likert scale***Table 2***Mean Ranges and Qualitative Descriptions for Level of Coping Strategies*

Mean Ranges	Qualitative Description
3.51-4.00	Highly Coping
2.51-3.50	Moderately Coping
1.51-2.50	Slightly Coping
1.00-1.50	Not Coping

Source: Valdez et al. (2020) for a 4-point Likert scale

Results and Discussion

Section 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3*Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents According to the Demographic Profile Variables (n=70)*

Profile Variable	Categories	f	%
Age	Early Adulthood (18-35)	24	34.3
	Middle Age (36-60)	29	41.4
	Later Maturity (over 60)	5	7.1
	No Answer	12	17.1
Sex	Male	10	14.3
	Female	60	85.7
Employment Status	Unemployed	33	47.1
	Self-Employed	19	27.1
	Employed	18	25.7
Educational Attainment	Elementary	12	17.1
	Secondary	25	35.7
	Tertiary/Bachelor's Degree	30	42.8
	Master's Degree	3	4.3
Family's Monthly Income	Less than P10,957	30	42.9
	Greater than or equal to P10,957 but less than P21,194	19	27.1
	Greater than or equal to P21,194 but less than P43,828	7	10.0
	Greater than or equal to P43,828 but less than P76,669	5	7.1
	Greater than or equal to P76,669 but less than P131,484	2	2.9
	Greater than or equal to P219,140	2	2.9
Relation to the Child	No Answer	5	7.1
	Father	8	11.4
	Mother	42	60.0
	Other close relative/family member	17	24.3
	Hired nanny	3	4.3

Table 3 presents the respondents' demographic profile, including age, sex, employment status, education, income, and relation to the child. Most respondents (41.4%) are middle-aged (36–60 years), a stage linked to physiological and psychological adjustments (Alibudbud, 2023). Early adulthood follows at 34.3%, while 17.1% did not report their age.

Women dominate the sample (85.7%), aligning with research showing greater female involvement in children's education (Norman et al., 2023). Nearly half (47.1%) are unemployed, which may negatively impact children's academic performance (Mari, 2023). Educational attainment varies, with 42.8% holding a bachelor's degree, while 42.9% earn below P10,957 monthly. Mothers make up the majority (60%) of caregivers, reinforcing findings that they are four times more involved in their child's education than fathers (Norman et al., 2023).

Table 4

Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Child's Condition (n=68)

Child's Condition	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
<i>Sensory Impairment</i>				
Vision (blindness or blurred vision)	7	10.3	61	89.7
Hearing (deaf or hard on hearing)	1	1.5	67	98.5
<i>Developmental Disabilities</i>				
Autism Spectrum Disorder	20	29.4	48	70.6
Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder	8	11.8	60	88.2
Intellectual Disability	10	14.7	58	85.3
<i>Genetic Disorders</i>				
Down's Syndrome	3	4.4	65	95.6
Fragile X Syndrome	0	0.0	68	100.0
Turner Syndrome	0	0.0	68	100.0
<i>Communication Disorders</i>				
Speech and Language Disorders	23	33.8	45	66.2

Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents based on their child's condition. Most reported speech and language disorders (33.8%), followed by autism spectrum disorder (29.4%) and intellectual disability (14.7%). UNICEF (2022) previously identified intellectual disability as the most common, while a Mandaluyong study found autism and intellectual disability dominant (Development Academy of the Philippines, 2022). This study differs, highlighting communication disorders as most prevalent in the surveyed SPED centers.

Section 2. Level of Parental Resilience of the Respondents

Table 5

Means and Standard Deviation for the Level of Parental Resilience of the Respondents

Statements		Mean	SD	Level
Factor 1: Knowledge of the child's characteristics				
	I know what my child is not good at.	5.33	1.742	Slightly Agree
2.	I know what my child will do in the future.	4.56	1.862	Slightly Agree
3.	I can figure out the reason behind my child's trouble.	5.37	1.661	Slightly Agree
4.	I'm aware of my child's traits.	5.74	1.639	Moderately Agree
5.	I have better knowledge of children's behavior and traits than others.	4.89	1.885	Slightly Agree
6.	I know what my child is best suited for. (e.g., school subjects and play)	5.36	1.703	Slightly Agree
Overall Factor 1		5.2071	1.14047	Resilient
Factor 2: Perceived social supports				
7.	I have someone who I can talk to about child-raising.	5.11	1.647	Slightly Agree
8.	I have someone who I can trust my child with.	5.33	1.674	Slightly Agree
9.	I'm worried about raising my child without anyone's opinion.	4.81	2.038	Slightly Agree
10.	There is someone who helps my child when he/she is in trouble.	5.29	1.737	Slightly Agree
11.	I have no choice but to raise my child all alone.	3.56	2.224	Neutral
12.	There are people who will help my child in the future.	5.13	1.719	Slightly Agree
Overall Factor 2		4.8714	1.21722	Resilient
Factor 3: Positive perception of parenting				
13.	I value interactions with my child.	5.73	1.849	Moderately Agree
14.	My child makes me feel energized.	5.60	1.789	Moderately Agree
15.	I enjoy talking to and playing with my child.	5.56	1.870	Moderately Agree
16.	I can do anything for my child that he needs.	5.63	1.851	Moderately Agree
Overall Factor 3		5.6286	1.74286	Very Resilient

Table 5 presents the respondents' level of parental resilience. In Factor 1: Knowledge of the child's characteristics, they slightly to moderately agreed that resilience comes from understanding their child's traits ($M=5.74$, $s=1.639$), with an overall mean of 5.2071 ($s=1.14047$).

For Factor 2: Perceived social support, respondents slightly agreed with most statements but were neutral about raising their child alone ($M=3.56$, $s=2.224$). Their highest agreement was with having someone they trust with their child ($M=5.33$, $s=1.674$), leading to an overall mean of 4.8714 ($s=1.21722$), showing resilience through social support.

In Factor 3: Positive perception of parenting, they moderately agreed with all statements, especially valuing interactions with their child ($M=5.73$, $s=1.849$). Their overall mean of 5.6286 ($s=1.74286$) indicates strong resilience through a positive parenting outlook.

In general, the respondents range from resilient to very resilient, with social support playing a key role. This aligns with Lasco et al. (2022), who highlighted support groups as crucial for resilience in parenting children with special needs. Additionally, Lasco et al. and Arabis-Quijote et al. (2023) found that Filipino parents maintain a positive outlook despite challenges.

Section 3. Level of Coping Strategies of the Respondents

Table 6

Means and Standard Deviation for the Level of Coping Strategies of the Respondents

Statements	Mean	SD	Level
Avoidant Coping Strategy			
I've been turning to work or other activities to take my mind off things.	2.89	1.186	A medium amount
2. I've been saying to myself "this isn't real".	2.37	1.119	A little bit
3. I've been using alcohol or other drugs to make myself feel better.	1.03	.293	I haven't been doing this at all
4. I've been giving up trying to deal with it.	1.96	1.109	A little bit
5. I've been refusing to believe that it has happened.	2.21	1.153	A little bit
6. I've been using alcohol or other drugs to help me get through it.	1.14	.873	I haven't been doing this at all
7. I've been giving up the attempt to cope.	1.94	1.273	A little bit
8. I've been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, sleeping, or shopping.	2.74	1.293	A medium amount
Avoidant Mean	2.0357	.64414	Slightly Coping
Problem-Focused Coping Strategy			
I've been concentrating my efforts on doing something about the situation I'm in.	3.43	.972	A medium amount
2. I've been taking action to try to make the situation better.	3.40	.954	A medium amount
3. I've been getting help and advice from other people.	2.97	1.251	A medium amount
4. I've been trying to see it in a different light, to make it seem more positive.	3.20	1.071	A medium amount
5. I've been trying to come up with a strategy about what to do.	3.20	1.124	A medium amount
6. I've been looking for something good in what is happening.	3.23	1.024	A medium amount
7. I've been trying to get advice or help from other people about what to do.	2.66	1.250	A medium amount
8. I've been thinking hard about what steps to take.	3.40	.969	A medium amount
Problem-Focused Mean	3.1857	.72411	Moderately Coping
Emotion-Focused Coping Strategy			
I've been getting emotional support from others.	2.63	1.079	A medium amount
2. I've been saying things to let my unpleasant feelings escape.	3.19	.997	A medium amount
3. I've been criticizing myself.	1.83	1.191	A little bit
4. I've been getting comfort and understanding from someone.	3.00	1.103	A medium amount
5. I've been making jokes about it.	2.27	1.154	A little bit
6. I've been accepting the reality of the fact that it has happened.	3.39	1.026	A medium amount
7. I've been expressing my negative feelings.	3.10	1.079	A medium amount
8. I've been trying to find comfort in my religion or spiritual beliefs.	3.34	.991	A medium amount
9. I've been learning to live with it.	3.17	.992	A medium amount
10. I've been blaming myself for things that happened.	2.06	1.178	A little bit
11. I've been praying or meditating.	3.27	.947	A medium amount
12. I've been making fun of the situation.	2.47	1.113	A little bit
Emotion-Focused Mean	2.8095	.66230	Moderately Coping

Table 6 presents the respondents' coping strategies. In avoiding coping, they moderately engage in distractions like work or entertainment ($M=2.89$, $s=1.186$), with minimal denial or substance use. Overall, they slightly use this strategy ($M=2.0357$, $s=.64414$).

For problem-focused coping, they moderately take action to improve their situation, with the highest agreement on making efforts to solve challenges ($M=3.43$, $s=.972$). This suggests they actively seek solutions to difficulties in parenting children with special needs ($M=3.1857$, $s=.72411$). In emotion-focused coping, they moderately accept their child's condition ($M=3.39$, $s=1.026$) and find comfort in religion ($M=3.34$, $s=.991$), aligning with findings by Lasco et al. (2022) and Berdan &

Distor (2024) on religion's role in resilience. Overall, they use this strategy moderately ($M=2.8095$, $s=.66230$).

Comparing strategies, respondents rely most on problem-focused coping ($M=3.1857$), followed by emotion-focused ($M=2.8095$) and avoidant coping ($M=2.0357$). This aligns with Haytham et al. (2022), who highlight problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies as effective. Munro (2023) further supports problem-focused coping as a direct stress management method, helping caregivers focus on improving their and their children's quality of life.

Section 4. Tests of Significant Differences in the Level of Parental Resilience and Level of Coping Strategies of the Respondents

Table 7

Tests of Significant Differences in the Respondents' Level of Resilience When Grouped According to Their Profile Variables

Profile Variables		K		PSS		PPP		
		Mean	p	Mean	p	Mean	p	
Age	Early Adulthood	5.000	.609	4.569	.128	5.521	.735	
	Middle Age	5.282		4.862		5.517		
	Later Maturity	5.400		5.767		6.150		
Sex	Male	4.750	.173	4.233	.073	4.675	.061	
	Female	5.283		4.978		5.788		
Employment Status	Unemployed	5.111	.653	5.076	.252	5.727	.815	
	Self-Employed	5.412		4.886		5.671		
	Employed	5.167		4.482		5.403		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	5.125	.447	5.319	.205	5.333	.546	
	Secondary	5.247		4.747		5.440		
	Tertiary/Bachelor's Degree	5.111		4.756		5.800		
	Master's Degree	6.167		5.278		6.667		
Child's Condition	Vision	Yes	5.405	.256	4.810	.939	6.036	.504
		No	5.164		4.847		5.562	
	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Yes	5.158	.888	4.750	.684	5.425	.579
		No	5.201		4.882		5.688	
	ADHD	Yes	5.479	.445	5.521	.091	6.125	.383
		No	5.150		4.753		5.542	
	Intellectual Disability	Yes	5.317	.702	5.183	.338	5.725	.825
		No	5.167		4.785		5.591	
	Down's Syndrome	Yes	4.167	.338	4.944	.976	5.917	.976
		No	5.236		4.839		5.596	
	Communication Disorders	Yes	5.203	.942	4.739	.615	5.533	.797
		No	5.182		4.896		5.650	
Family's Monthly Income (FMI)	FMI < P10,957	5.039	.387	4.628	.144	5.350	.109	
	P10,957 ≤ FMI ≤ P21,194	5.421		5.061		6.276		
	P21,194 ≤ FMI ≤ P43,828	4.952		4.619		5.286		
	P43,828 ≤ FMI ≤ P76,669	5.633		5.167		6.600		
	P76,669 ≤ FMI ≤ P131,484	5.333		6.417		6.875		
	FMI ≥ P219,140	6.500		5.917		3.500		
Relation to the Child	Father	4.667	.269	4.250	.166	4.281	.095	
	Mother	5.171		4.722		5.595		
	Other close relative/family member	5.471		5.422		6.221		
	Hired nanny	5.667		5.500		6.333		

*K-knowledge of the child's characteristics; PSS- perceived social supports; PPP-positive perception of parenting

Table 7 presents the means and p-values for differences in parental resilience based on respondents' profile variables. No significant differences were found across age groups ($p > 0.05$), though females had slightly higher resilience scores ($K=5.283$, $PSS=4.978$, $PPP=5.788$) than males. Employment status also showed no significant effect, but self-employed individuals had slightly higher resilience. While education level did not yield significant differences, respondents with a master's degree had the highest resilience scores ($K=6.167$, $PSS=5.278$, $PPP=6.667$). Similarly, no significant differences were found based on children's conditions or family income, though those earning $\geq P219,140$ had higher scores in knowledge and social support but lower in positive perception of parenting. Notably, relatives and nannies showed higher resilience than parents.

These findings suggest that parental resilience is not determined by demographic factors but rather by their understanding of their child's needs, perceived social support, and positive parenting perception. This contrasts with Bhattacharjee et al. (2022), who linked resilience to education, occupation, and income, but aligns with Rajan et al. (2016) that resilience is independent of age and gender. While external factors may influence resilience (Widyawati et al., 2022), the study highlights that parents of children with special needs adapt well regardless of socioeconomic status.

Hence, to further understand how they deal with their situations, the role of their profile variables in their coping strategies was also explored, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8

Tests of Significant Differences in the Respondents' Level of Coping Strategies When Grouped According to Their Profile Variables

Profile Variables		K		PSS		PPP		
		Mean	p	Mean	p	Mean	p	
Age	Early Adulthood	2.005*	.040	3.240	.715	2.851	.121	
	Middle Age	2.039		3.211		2.813		
	Later Maturity	2.725*		3.450		3.317		
Sex	Male	1.975	.750	2.975	.324	2.750	.761	
	Female	2.046		3.221		2.819		
Employment Status	Unemployed	2.106	.307	3.148	.626	2.806	.793	
	Self-Employed	2.105		3.322		2.886		
	Employed	1.833		3.111		2.736		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	2.458*	.039	3.240	.342	3.028	.519	
	Secondary	2.015		3.030		2.713		
	Tertiary/Bachelor's Degree	1.879*		3.304		2.789		
	Master's Degree	2.083		3.083		2.944		
Child's Condition	Vision	Yes	2.464	.043	3.286	.711	2.964	.498
		No	1.957		3.176		2.781	
	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Yes	1.719	.013	3.188	1.00	2.667	.292
		No	2.130		3.188		2.856	
	ADHD	Yes	2.219	.322	3.281	.703	3.094	.189
		No	1.981		3.175		2.761	
	Intellectual Disability	Yes	2.025	.933	3.375	.384	2.933	.500
		No	2.007		3.155		2.777	
	Down's Syndrome	Yes	1.875	.549	3.000	.353	2.444	.281
		No	2.015		3.196		2.817	
	Communication Disorders	Yes	1.940	.524	3.120	.588	2.685	.313
		No	2.044		3.222		2.859	
Family's Monthly Income (FMI)	FMI < P10,957	2.217	.111	3.196	.031*	2.836	.085	
	P10,957 \leq FMI \leq P21,194	2.033		3.401		2.974		

Profile Variables	K		PSS		PPP		
	Mean	p	Mean	p	Mean	p	
P21,194 ≤FMI≤ P43,828	1.893		3.286		3.000		
P43,828 ≤FMI≤ P76,669	1.950		3.275		2.733		
P76,669≤FMI≤ P131,484	1.938		3.750		2.917		
FMI≥ P219,140	.500		.500		.208		
Relation to the Child	Father	1.891	.099	2.938	.126	2.698	.033+
	Mother	1.908		3.128		2.687	
	Another close relative/fam. member	2.353		3.463		3.103	
	Hired nanny	2.417		3.083		3.167	

Table 8 shows the differences in coping strategies among parents of children with special needs based on their profile variables. Significant differences were found in avoidant coping, with older parents and those with only elementary education using it more. Parents of children with visual impairments also showed higher avoidant coping, while those with children on the autism spectrum showed lower. No significant differences were found in problem-focused or emotion-focused coping across most variables, including sex, employment, and educational attainment. Though income and relation to the child showed some trends, they were not statistically significant. The findings suggest that coping strategies are influenced more by behavioral and psychological factors than by demographics.

Section 5. Program Proposal for Parents of Children with Special Needs

The study examined the demographic profile, resilience, and coping strategies of primary caregivers of children with special needs. Most respondents were middle-aged, unemployed females with tertiary education. While they demonstrated varying levels of resilience, key contributors included knowledge of their child's needs, social support, and positive parenting perceptions. Problem-focused and emotion-focused coping were commonly used, though few significant differences were found across demographic variables, suggesting that other factors influence coping and resilience. The findings support the development of a program called "**PROTECT: Parental Resources, Opportunities, Training, Education, and Connections in a Team,**" designed to strengthen caregiver support networks under the guidance of social workers.

Table 9

Program Proposal for Primary Caregivers of Children with Special Needs

Parts of the Proposal	Description
Title	PROTECT: Parental Resources, Opportunities, Training, Education, and Connections in a Team
Areas of Focus	Family and Community Development School Social Work
Project Site	Municipalities of Solano and Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Cagayan Valley, Philippines
Proponents	Department of Psychology, Human Services, and Social Work Marian Social Work Organization
Program Rationale	According to the results, primary caregivers of children with special needs in the province experience a variety of parenting, resiliency, and coping strategies. Despite having no significant differences among demographic groups, the study emphasizes the importance of specialized assistance programs to meet the unique requirements of these parents. The PROTECT initiative strives to empower primary caregivers and improve their and their children's quality of life by providing comprehensive resources, opportunities, training, education, and connections in a sustainable community.
Program Objectives	To enhance primary caregivers' knowledge and skills in parenting children with special needs. To foster a supportive community among primary caregivers of children with special needs. To improve parental resilience and coping strategies.

Parts of the Proposal	Description
	To facilitate access to relevant resources and services for primary caregivers and their children.
Phases	<p>Follow-Up Needs Assessment: The team will discuss the results of this research with the teachers and the primary caregivers. An open forum will be conducted for the primary caregivers to clarify and raise questions. An activity evaluation will be conducted after.</p> <p>Materials Development The team will create a technical working group (in collaboration with significant stakeholders) in planning for an educational material to be developed. The TWG will carefully select the most appropriate media to communicate with the primary caregivers about the effective parenting techniques that foster resiliency. The TWG will design the selected medium that will capture not only the interest of the primary caregivers but also their capabilities based on their demographic characteristics (such as linguistic requirements). The design will go through several consultations and revisions until a final product achieves the consensus of the TWG. It will also be evaluated by at least three evaluators (a special needs educator, a parent, and a social worker) outside the program sites. The final output will be published through a publisher that meets both reasonable price and quality.</p> <p>Implementation In the Comprehensive Parenting Education activity of the program, the team will again meet with the primary caregivers not only to distribute the materials but to discuss the usefulness of the materials as well as their responsibilities. Since these primary caregivers are required to attend PTA conferences in the school, this opportunity shall be made better through this discussion with the involvement of a registered social worker and other necessary professionals. During the PTA conferences, a sustainable Support Group for Primary caregivers will be formed through the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Recruitment and formation b. Initial meetings c. Ongoing support and facilitation d. Sustainability planning e. Outreach and expansion f. Evaluation will be conducted at the end of each session with the primary caregivers.

Figure 3
Program Paradigm for Primary Caregivers of Children with Special Needs

Figure 3 shows a program centered on the primary caregiver and child with special needs, supported by teachers, social workers, and professionals. The program focuses on three key activities: needs assessment, comprehensive parenting education, and support groups. Parenting education promotes problem-focused coping, while support groups strengthen emotion-focused coping through empathy and connection. The enclosed design symbolizes the protection and care provided by the surrounding community.

Conclusion

1. Based on the respondents' demographic profile, most primary caregivers of children with special needs are female, middle-aged, and unemployed. Most come from lower-class backgrounds and have completed at least a tertiary education. Furthermore, mothers are the primary carers, indicating a sex difference in the involvement of primary caregiver in their children's schooling. The most common conditions are developmental disorders, which are different from previous research and may indicate particular difficulties experienced by the participants.
2. In terms of parental resilience, the primary caregiver of children with special needs are resilient through knowing their children's conditions and having sufficient social support, while they stay very resilient through having a positive perception of parenting their children, valuing their interactions with them despite difficulties in communicating or moderating behaviors that are realities among persons with disabilities.
3. In their coping strategies, it was found that the primary caregivers generally use problem-focused coping strategies, emphasizing the importance of understanding their situations, actively seeking solutions, and identifying courses of action for better parenting of their children. The primary caregivers were also moderately coping using emotion-focused coping strategies, and only slightly coping using avoidant coping strategies.
4. The primary caregivers' age, sex, employment status, educational attainment, child's condition, and family's monthly income do not describe how resilient they are in parenting children with special needs. On the other hand, older primary caregivers and those with elementary education rely significantly more on avoidant coping strategies. In contrast, primary caregivers of children with autism rely significantly less on avoidant coping.
5. The program proposal for primary caregivers of children with special needs was crafted to be relevant to the existing resilience and coping strategies

Recommendations

1. To the **primary caregivers of children with special needs**, regardless of their personal or professional profile, they should sustain their resilience by continuously educating themselves about the condition of their children, seeking social support, and maintaining a positive perception that their children are just like any other children. They should consider taking educational opportunities to understand their challenges and address these through appropriate coping strategies.
2. To the **teachers of children with special needs**, they should help the primary caregivers understand the children's conditions by religiously preparing valid and reliable reports of the children's achievements and their observations to be shared with the primary caregivers in appropriate set-ups, publicly or privately. They should support primary caregivers not only as teachers but also as confidantes in difficult times of parenting children with special needs.

3. To the **school administrators**, they should provide avenues for the primary caregivers of children with special needs to gather, share, and discuss helpful information as a way to support each other.
4. To the **social workers**, they should continue exploring opportunities to understand and support primary caregivers of children with special needs, extending to their families to ensure resilience and effective coping amidst challenges in their situations. They should also consider reviewing the program proposed in this study, refining it, and implementing it thereafter for the identified primary caregivers of children with special needs.
5. To the **future researchers**, they may consider the following:
 - a. Explore other variables among the primary caregivers of children with special needs that may have direct relationship with resilience and coping strategies (cognitive and behavioral constructs);
 - b. Conduct case studies specific about a special need to deepen their understanding and propose disability-specific programs for the primary caregivers; and
 - c. Differentiate the parents of children without special needs and parents of children with special needs to involve the former in supporting the latter.

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